

MALA SIDDHANTA: AN AYURVEDIC INSIGHT INTO EXCRETORY PHYSIOLOGY WITH SPECIAL EMPHASIS TO PURISHA

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ABSTRACT

The *Mala* consists of the three primary waste products of the human body as recognized in Ayurveda; *Purisha*, *Mutra* and *Sweda*. These *Malas* are incredibly important in maintaining balance in one's body, helping with detoxifying the body, and supporting the overall functional integrity of the body. *Purisha* is the solid part of the waste product of digestion; *Mutra* is the liquid waste produced mainly from the filtering process of the kidneys; and *Sweda* is the vapour or perspiration which comes from perspiration out through the large pores of the skin and is vital to thermo-regulate and to remove metabolic waste through perspiration. The production, change, and removal of the *Malas* depend on the proper functioning of *Agni* and the free flow of *Srotas*. This article discusses the definition of *Mala Siddhanta* from a physiological, clinical, and pathological perspective about *Purisha* and why this is an important concept in relation to health and disease.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, *Purisha*, *Malas*, *Waste*, *Mutra*, *Sweda*.

INTRODUCTION

According to Ayurveda, *Trimala* comprises the three primary products excreted by the body; *Purisha*, *Mutra* and *Sweda*, they are seen as vital for balancing the body internally, as well as for health overall. Their correct formation and elimination on time is an indicator of good physiologic health, and if any or all of them are not formed or excreted correctly, *Amavisha* can build up and the body's *Doshas* can be vitiated, which will lead to metabolic disorders. Amongst the three waste products (*Trimala*) of body *Purisha* is considered important one for physiological and pathological point of view.^[1-4]

Trimala Siddhanta

✓ *Mutra* is formed by the kidneys and excretes the body's nitrogen waste products, excess salts from the blood, and metabolic by-products, as well as playing a role in maintaining the electrolytes and fluid balances in the body. In Ayurveda, *Mutra* is considered to be closely related to the body's water metabolism, and is often referred to as being associated with the *Pitta*

Dosha. The amount, color and frequency of urine may indicate whether there is a Systemic disorder, for example: diabetes or renal disease.

✓ *Sweda* is an important factor in thermoregulation as well as detoxification and skin health by removing metabolic waste and regulating body temperature. From an ayurvedic perspective, both *Pitta* and *Kapha Doshas* have a relationship with *Sweda*. An abundance or deficiency of *Sweda* indicates a Metabolic or Regulatory imbalance.

✓ *Purisha* is the final product of digestion occurring in the large intestine and its purpose is to remove from the body all of the undigested leftover food, metabolic waste products and toxins that have built up during the process. The formation of *Purisha* also depends upon having a proper *Agni*, as well as good dietary habits especially in regards to the amount of fibers consumed. Any problems with the formation or excretion of *Purisha* can lead to gastrointestinal problems such as

Vibandha, *Atisara* and other malabsorption problems. The Ayurvedic texts stresses that how important *Purisha* in cleaning out the gastrointestinal tract and achieving balance in the entire system.^[4-6]

Importance of *Trimala*

Health is not just dependent on the nourishment of tissue; it is also dependent upon the proper production and elimination of the waste products of the body. The *Malas* (waste) of body are important byproducts of metabolism that help to maintain balance and homeostasis within the body. The formation and timely elimination of *Trimala* indicates the proper functioning of *Agni*, *Dosha* and *Srotas*. The *Purisha* assists in providing structural support to the body and also regulates the *Vata Dosha*; proper elimination of *Purisha* help to maintain gastrointestinal health and prevent diseases of gastrointestinal origin. *Mutra* supports the balance of fluids, the equilibrium of electrolytes and the elimination of water-soluble toxins, which is important in order to maintain both renal and systemic health. *Sweda* regulates the temperature of the body, supports the integrity of the skin and assists in the removal of metabolic waste through perspiration. Any deviation in quantity, quality

or elimination of these *Malas* would signify an imbalance in *Dosha*; and could serve as an early diagnostic indicator for the onset of disease. *Trimala* is an integral part of both the detoxification process and in maintaining the equilibrium of the *Dhatu* as well as optimal health.^[5-7]

Purisha

Purisha is associated with the *Purishadhara Kala* of the body which is located in the area of the *Pakwashaya* and *Udika*, where *Purisha* and *Mutra* separate. The *Purishavaha Srotas* have their *Mula* in the large intestine and rectum, and are therefore the channels of the body responsible for the formation, transport and elimination of feces. The partition of consumed food into *Sara* and *Kitta* explain the *Utpatti* of *Purisha*. *Kitta*'s liquid component separates into *Mutra*, while its solid component becomes *Purisha*.

Ayurveda categorizes *Purisha* into many forms (Figure 1) According to the *Purishavaha Srotas*' anomalies. *Purisha Pariksha* is used to assess these changes which show underlying *Dosha* involvement.

Figure 1: Various types of *Purisha*.

Atidrava types of *Pariksha* involve vitiation of *Pitta* or *Kapha Dosha* which is frequently associated with liquid or semi-solid feces. *Atigrathitam* types of *Pariksha* are associated with dryness and *Vata* aggravation, indicated hard & lumpy stools. *Sashabda* types of *Pariksha* having excessive flatus or sound during defecation, while *Sashula* types of *Pariksha* are associated with painful bowel movements. As a result, the Ayurvedic interpretation of *Purisha* emphasizes its significance in the diagnosis and treatment of gastrointestinal illnesses by integrating morphological, physiological and pathological aspects.^[6-8]

Clinical Relevance of *Purisha*

Purisha Pariksha is an important part of Ayurveda's diagnostics, both regarding gastrointestinal and systemic wellness. Its analysis is done according to color, consistency, smell, volume, and the presence of mucus, bubbles and other associated symptoms.

- ✓ *Saama Purisha* is heavy and foul-smelling and can be seen with constipation and/or abdominal pain.
- ✓ *Niraama Purisha* is lighter, less odor and can indicate that a person has a healthy digestion.
- ✓ *Purisha Vriddhi* results in abdominal distention and fullness.
- ✓ *Purisha Kshaya* results in a gurgling sound in the intestines, distended abdomen with discomfort arising from excess gas in the intestines.
- ✓ *Raktayukta Purisha* may declare possibility of ulcers or hemorrhoids (*Arsha*) or fissures such as ulcerative colitis.
- ✓ *Krimiyukta Purisha* is indicative of intestinal parasite infestation.
- ✓ *Amayukta Purisha* containing undigested food remnants and sensation of dullness after passing stool suggests the presence of *Ama* and restricted gastric digestive fire.

✓ *Atyartham Gandhiyukta Purisha* (foul-smelling stool) often indicating putrefaction, infectious conditions and possibly diseases like *Grahani*.^[7-9]

Dosha and Purisha

Pathological changes in *Purisha* are also related to *Dosha* imbalances in Ayurveda. In *Vata dosha* predominance, the stool will tend to be *Alpalpam*, *Shushkam* as well as occasionally *Picchila*; therefore, the patient may also present with symptoms of abdominal distension, colicky abdominal pain and/or excessive flatulence. In *Pitta dosha*, the stool would generally be *Atidrava* and *Pittasamsrishta*, often with a sensation of heat and urgency of defecation. In *Kapha dosha*, the stool will be *Atipicchila*, *Guru* and *Snigdha*; therefore the patient may complain of slow digestion, feeling of heavy weight in their abdomen and lethargy, etc. In *Sannipataja (Tridoshaja)* conditions, there are alternations between *Vibandha* and *Atisara* resulting in irregularity of bowel movements and unpredictable digestion.^[4-6]

Approaches to balance Trimala Physiology

Good sources of fiber, drinking enough fluids and avoiding foods that are very processed and very spicy will help to promote good bowel-elimination and the normal elimination of *Mutra*. Regular exercise, practicing *Yoga* and performing *Abhyanga* promote normal sweating and good circulation. *Panchakarma* therapies including *Swedana*, *Basti* and *Virechana* are also helps to maintain excretory balance of body. There are several classical Ayurvedic herbal preparations that are used to support the proper regulation of bowel function, support healthy urinary function, and maintain the normal levels of sweating, including: *Gokshura*, *Triphala*, *Haridra* and *Punarnava* etc.^[8-10]

CONCLUSION

The framework of Ayurveda considered *Malas (Purisha, Mutra and Sweda)* as not only metabolic waste products but also vital indicators of systemic balance. Therefore, their proper formation, quantity, and elimination demonstrate how well the *Agni*, *Srotas* and the *Doshas* are functioning. Any alterations in these *Malas* during states of imbalance demonstrate not only local dysfunction but also more profound systemic derangements that could affect both physical and mental health. Characteristics of stool directly correspond to the balance of the gut microbiome; the method of urine excretion reflects the degree of renal function and metabolic regulation; and sweat is necessary for both thermoregulation and removing toxins from the body.

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